

HOW TO CONDUCT THE LESSON BY USING INDUCTIVE AND DEDUCTIVE WAY OF METHODOLOGIES IN THE CLASSROOM

Kamilova Rozakhon Dilshod qizi

The teacher of "General philology" department,
Urgench state pedagogical institute

Ollanazarova Shohnozha Norbek qizi

The student of Foreign language and literature department,
Urgench state pedagogical institute

***Annotation.** This article defines the difference between inductive and deductive method, how to use inductive and deductive way of teaching in an appropriate way in the classroom as well he advantages and disadvantages of both methodologies.*

***Defining article:** Differentiating inductive and deductive teaching*

- 1) Describing two type of teaching approach*
- 2) Advantages of inductive and deductive approach*
- 3) Disadvantages of both approach*
- 4) Role of teacher and students in the classroom*
- 5) Conclusion*

***Key words:** inductive, deductive, rule-driven, rule-discovery, student-centered, teacher-centered.*

There are two types of approach to teach the grammar: inductive and deductive approaches. Both of them have pros and cons to the language learners in the classroom. It depends on some factors, say, the performance of the teacher and students and the way that lesson conducted. However, both inductive and deductive teaching have more benefits, especially for the ESL classes for teaching and learning the lesson in an appropriate way. Haight, Heron and Cole (2007) stated that: "Some agreements exists that the most effective grammar teaching includes some deductive and inductive characteristics".

First of all, inductive way of teaching also called rule-discovery starts with making specific examples and then followed by general rules. It is a teaching method which students discover rules by themselves by observing examples. Students are at the center of the lesson. In this method, teachers play a role as a guide. Because they only give instructions to their students about what to do or not to do. Teacher does not give any general rule related to the topic at the beginning of the lesson. He or she can

only ask if they know a little bit about the topic. The reason why young language learners prefer inductive way of teaching is its advantages for students. Also with the help of this method, they can improve their creativity, critical thinking, problem solving, oral communication and so on. First, this approach is so meaningful and easy to remember rather than learning academic and complex rules. Another beneficial side is that this type of teaching encourages students to become autonomy learners. During researching for information to the topic, students go to the library or search from the internet. At that time they read magazines, books and articles, also use different internet tools like Canva, Prezi.com and so on. While doing this, they will learn a lot of information by themselves and this helps them moving from teacher dependency towards independent learners. The lesson which is conducted inductively will be more productive, game-based and fun. This engages student's active participation. However how much beneficial it may appear, there are some disadvantages of inductive teaching. During the lesson, students can hypothesize the wrong rule. It can create inequality. Because all students will not respond equally well. Additionally, this way of teaching is so much time and energy consuming, it requires extra planning for conducting the lesson. Also, this method is considered not suitable for introvert learners. Besides inductive approach requires to be at the center of the audience and be more active, while introverts feel shy and embarrassed when giving a talk.

Second approach is deductive which is a type of teaching include theoretical rules at the beginning of the lesson and then continued with grammar test for better understanding. Also called a traditional way of grammar teaching. According to the Thornbury's three basic principles a deductive lesson starts with the presentation of the rules by teacher. Secondly teacher gives examples by highlighting the grammar structures. Then students make practice with the rules and produce their own examples at the end of the lesson (Thornbury, 1999). The lesson starts like this, "Hello everyone, today we are going to learn past perfect tense with past participle verbs. Past perfect tense is formed with a past tense form of the verb "to have" plus the past participle of the verb and do on". This is how all the rules driven by the teacher. Deductive way of teaching is more rule focused and gets straight to the point. Additionally, it is easy to cover all the information in short period of time. In the inductive way of teaching approach students play a main role, but in the deductive they play a role as a passive recipient. Another beneficial side is difficult grammar point can be presented in an easy way. On the other hand, if lesson continued by only teacher's explanation of the rules, it may result teacher dependency. It results students perform more passively and cannot make a decision from their own. In my opinion, starting with a grammar rules is not interesting, especially for young learners and less memorable for them.

Conclusion

The importance of both methodologies during the lesson is so beneficial and can give good results to the language learners. Inductive way of teaching is more active during the lesson rather than being passive recipient. While it might be appropriate at time to introduce a rule and then moving to examples. Nevertheless, there are positives and negatives to both inductive and deductive approaches and a combination of both grammar teaching approaches can be more efficient in the long run, at least some learners.

References:

1. <https://outpeltglobalblog.com>
2. <https://www.birmingham.ac.uk>